

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

Doniyorov B.N.¹, Doniyorov N.N.²

¹Bukhara State University, Teacher of the Department of Ecology and Geography.

²Bukhara State University, Teacher of the Department of Mathematics.

ABSTRACT: The article discusses the historical glory of the beekeeping industry, the use of bee products in the treatment of various diseases, the role of honey in the quantitative and qualitative changes in the human body, the need for honey as a biogenic substance, basic and additional valuable products from beekeeping some information such as bee breeds, the division of labor in stratified individuals in the family, the types of packages in which bees are fed, the criteria for the development of families, the time of swarming, the establishment of a new family.

KEYWORDS: Honey, bee baby, organism, growth, development, sensory organs, wax, pollen, nectar, propolis, bee's milk, biogenic substance, toxic secretions, placeholder, package, beekeeping, areal.

INTRODUCTION

Beekeeping is an ancient field, the first information about which can be found in the works of pre-Christian Egyptian medicine, the sacred book of Zoroastrianism "Avesto", the Indian book "Life", the science of medicine "Jud-ji". Even world scientists such as Homer, Democritus, Aristotle, and Hippocrates have noted the importance of honey in the treatment of many diseases. There is information that our great ancestor Abu Ali Ibn Sina prepared 500 types of bee products and Abu Rayhan Beruni prepared 300 types of medicines [4, 4; 6.3; 8].

For the growth, development and normal functioning of the sensory organs, the human body should consume 60-80 grams of pure honey per day [1, 522-524; 9]. However, this figure does not exceed 30-40 grams per person in the case of Bukhara region. Also due to the growing socio-medical need for valuable substances from beekeeping, the need to develop this area of practice is self-explanatory.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In collecting data on beekeeping, stationary observations were mainly based on local methods [7]. Several nests have been studied in different situations. A number of other observations were also made.

MAIN PART

Along with high-quality and healing honey, bee baby produce a number of biogenic substances, such as wax, pollen, propolis, glue, mother bee's milk, bee venom [2, 230-232]. These substances are processed and used for consumption in agriculture, medicine. In addition, in the pollination of plants, in the food chain [3] the role of curtain-winged helpers, which occupy the land-air environment, is fragmented. Therefore, beekeeping has become one of the oldest lucrative industries and one of the thousand treasures.

Climatic conditions of Bukhara region are due to the interaction of various factors, the geographical location of the region, the climatic features of the southern (subtropical) deserts, the tension between biological rhythms, partly sernam, changing spring, dry, hot summer, short, changeable autumn, sometimes warm, sometimes cold, windy winter, annual sunny days reach 2800-3000 hours, the total amount of radiation from the sun reaches 150-160 kcal / cm², the amount of atmospheric precipitation scarcity, lack of moisture, excessive water consumption by plants during transpiration, declining sap-separating plants make it necessary to relocate bees to honey-rich areas with strong juicing capacity. In view of the above, the feeding of bees in special

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

packages began in the second half of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century. Prior to that, beekeeping products were obtained primitively or remotely from beehives nesting under tree floors, abandoned appliances, house floors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the conditions of Bukhara region, locusts, Carpathians, carnica, ligustica and other breeds of children are raised in different types of packages, as a family. Of these, the local and Carpathian breeds have a large area due to their good adaptability and productivity compared to other breeds. One of the achievements in the field is that we have received from these breeds hybrids that are different from their parents, disease-resistant, highly viable and productive.

The bee family usually consists of a single queen, up to a thousand turtles, and many workers. But before the crisis, the family structure will change and restructure. In the Bukhara region, children earn more if they are raised in one- and two-bedroom packages. The packages are shown in Picture 1 below

Picture 1. View of one- and two-bedroom packages

For the good, uniform development of families, the number of frames in the packages is equalized. In this case, the age of the individuals in the frame, the amount of honey, pollen, seeds and mushrooms are considered appropriate. The fact that the number of frames in the package is eight or more indicates that the family of these children is developing well, and the expected primary biological productivity from it will be blessed.

The queen can lay eggs of her own weight per day, when the amount of pollen and pollen coming to the nest is equal and maximum. Otherwise, egg laying is somewhat limited. This means that the stability of the egg laying depends on the balance of pollen and pollen coming to the nest. The placement of the eggs in hexagonal wax cages does not duplicate each other. Picture 2 below shows the placement of bee eggs in hexagonal wax cages

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

Picture 2. Placement of bee eggs in hexagonal wax cages

Before laying an egg, the queen checks the condition and cleanliness of the wax cage with the help of sensitive organs in the head, and then lays the egg in the next part of the abdomen. When laying eggs, the sensitive hairs around the queen's ovipositor are affected by touching the wall of the wax cage, while the working children, on the contrary, develop from the eggs laid by the turtles.

From April to the end of June, the family grows and the groundwork is laid for a new princess. This situation can be seen in Picture 3 below

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

Picture 3. Pre-emergence activity in the bee family

The appearance of two princesses in the family causes one of them to fly away. Observations revealed temporary migration to phanerophytes such as apple, apricot, cherry, peach, common pine, almond, blackberry, ligustrum, and pomegranate. If there is no need to increase the number of families in the bee garden, the process of swarming can be controlled. Picture 4 below shows the migration of children

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

Picture 4. Bee migration

The migration will be packed in a new and clean package and practical assistance will be provided based on its needs. Migration is twice as fast for families with artificially divided bee baby. The developmental time of eggs from queens, turtles and working individuals varies depending on environmental conditions. For example, it takes 14-16 days for a princess, 20-21 days for a worker, and 24-25 days for a turiten.

CONCLUSION

Beekeeping has a history of many thousands of years, during which time they lived in trees and hollows in the rocks of the mountains.

The geographical location of Bukhara region, the climatic features of the southern (subtropical) deserts, the tension between biological rhythms, the lack of moisture, the decline of succulent plants make bees rich in nectar. There is a need to relocate to the affected areas. To do this, bees are now kept in special packages, which have become one of the thousand and one treasures, a lucrative branch of agriculture.

Honey, pollen-honey mixture, honey wax, wax, bee's milk, glue, toxic substances are extracted from bees to protect human health. Bees also pollinate flowering plants to meet their need for pollen and nectar, and higher plant populations play a role in maintaining the stability of the species and in the food chain.

Some Information about Beekeeping (On the Example of Bukhara Region)

Experiments show that the biogenic substances of honey and beekeeping benefit everyone equally. In particular, the growth and development of infants who consume honey every day is positive, and their susceptibility to disease is reduced. Adding honey to the diet of children in need of artificial feeding improves the gastrointestinal tract and normalizes the micro flora of the digestive system. However, the demand for beekeeping biogenic substances is relatively high in adolescents, the elderly and people who are exhausted due to illness.

In cosmetology, honey is used in the preparation of various creams and masks. These creams and masks rejuvenate and heal the skin.

Consumption of 60-80 grams of honey a day refreshes a person who spends a lot of energy. Even athletes taste honey and fruit juice when exercising.

Although all beekeeping products are used to strengthen the immune system and treat various diseases, overuse of bee products, including honey, can be allergenic. Therefore, when treating with honey, pollen, perga, propolis, etc., it is necessary to follow the existing instructions. Then beekeeping and its products will be of great value.

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